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LA CONFLUENCE: A STUDY OF THE INTERPLAY OF NON-COGNITIVE AND COGNITIVE FACTORS IN DETERMINING THE SUCCESS OF STUDENTS ON UNDERGRADUATE ENGINEERING PROGRAMMES

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ABSTRACT

Over the past twenty years, educational psychologists have become aware of the importance of non-cognitive factors on the academic success of students. The excitement generated by this research stems from the fact that many of these factors are learnt, and if detrimental to learning, can be unlearnt.

This paper looks at two key non-cognitive factors, Mindset, developed by Carol Dweck of Stanford University, which claims that people can have either of two mindsets, fixed or growth. A short test indicates into which category a student fits, and if it is the 'fixed' category, Dweck has a series of tutorials designed to move them into the growth mindset and improve their learning outcomes.

The second factor, Grit, was developed by Angela Duckworth of the University of Pennsylvania. Duckworth defines Grit as a combination of passion and perseverance, and through testing, she can determine a Grit score for each individual. This score, her research shows, is crucial for future success in life. Again, for individuals with a low Grit score, it is possible to learn how to be gritty.

This paper examines how Grit and Mindset score for engineering undergraduates correlate with academic success, and seeks to generate a single non-cognitive test that may be usefully employed to predict success for engineering students on their courses. This is a longer term goal, and is expected to take some three or four years follow-on work.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past twenty years, educational psychologists have become aware of the importance of non-cognitive factors on the academic success of students. The excitement generated by this research stems from the fact that many of these factors are learnt, and if detrimental to learning, can be unlearned.

The term 'non-cognitive' is, of course, a misnomer, as all the activity being studied is cognitive, just not traditionally academic. Durlak [1] suggests the phrase 'social and emotional learning', but it has proven difficult to shift the long-used term 'non-cognitive.'

This paper looks at two key non-cognitive factors, Mindset, developed by Carol Dweck of Stanford University, which claims that people can have either of two mindsets, fixed or growth. A short test indicates into which category a student fits, and if it is the 'fixed' category, Dweck has a series of tutorials designed to move them into the growth mindset and improve their learning outcomes.

The second factor, Grit, was developed by Angela Duckworth of the University of Pennsylvania. Duckworth defines Grit as a combination of passion and perseverance, and through testing, she can determine a Grit score for everyone. This score, her research shows, is crucial for future success in life. Again, for individuals with a low Grit score, it is possible to learn how to be gritty.

This paper examines how Grit and Mindset score for engineering undergraduates correlate with academic success, and seeks to generate a single non-cognitive test that may be usefully employed to predict success for engineering students on their courses. This is a longer-term goal, and is expected to take some three or four years' follow-on work.

2.0 BACKGROUND

Two rivers meet in the French city of Lyon, La Saône and Le Rhône, just south of the aptly named Presqu'île. Once past that point, it is impossible to tell what water came from which river.

Figure 1: The Rhone at Lyon

This is a good analogy for the difficulty in doing educational research, where so many factors, from both nature and nurture, blend together, making it difficult, if not impossible to isolate direct causality in research.

The Latin word *educare* means to ‘draw out.’ The role of education is to draw out the natural ability of the child, an ability that is the melding of their genetic heritage (their genotype) and their environment (both shared and non-shared). Behavioral geneticists study this interplay and have come up with some important insights [2].

Everyone knows that some children have an aptitude and a taste for traditional academic work. Both qualities are influenced—but not determined—by genes. These pupils are the easiest for schools to handle, and they tend to do well in the current system. They are also the pupils that selective schools pick out and whose successes are then claimed by the schools to be the result of a superior education. Current policies and the “blank slate” philosophy hold up these children as models. They suggest that if we work harder then all children can be made to fit this mold. As a result, current approaches push nonacademic children to become mediocre generalists regardless of their natural abilities, interests, hopes, and dreams.

Studies of reading by behavioral geneticists identifies the genetic component as being between 60 and 80%. Knowing this, the task of the educator is to use the genes to their best advantage in each case, meaning that education, from primary to tertiary, should be personalized.

2.1 MINDSET

The US psychologist, Carol Dweck [3], identifies two mindsets, fixed and growth. Fixed minds make little effort, relying on their ability. If their ability is not enough, they quit, usually blaming someone or something for their failure.

Growth mindset people know they have to work. They accept failure along the way as a challenge, a lesson, not a reason to give up.

The fixed mindset is easy. You don’t have to do any work, because you either have it or you don’t. If you don’t succeed, it’s not your fault, it’s someone else’s: your teacher, the referee, your boss.

The growth people enjoy working to succeed, enjoying the challenge of getting there.

Malcolm Gladwell [4] put a rough number on the effort hours needed for complete mastery: 10,000. He reckons that’s roughly the hours put in by diverse people, from a teenage Bill gates on his computer, to the young Beatles in Hamburg. Before their amazing success, there were years of work which moved them up a level from the rest of us.

Dweck has devised an eight-item self-answered survey, with a six-point Likert answer scale with possible responses ranging from ‘disagree a lot’ to ‘agree a lot’.

The key lesson from Dweck’s work is that Mindset is acquired, and can be changed. She has devised online workshops to help people make the change from fixed to growth mindsets, and this has resulted in improved academic scores.

2.2 GRIT

Grit for much of 20th century America was seen as an essential individual virtue to foster the frontier spirit that had made America great. In the early 21st century, grit was reinvented as an educational virtue by Angela Duckwork of the University of

Pennsylvania. Duckworth was a student of Martin Seligman, one of a number of graduate students in the 1960s who rebelled against the orthodoxy of American psychology, B. F. Skinner's behaviourism. Skinner had little time for conscious thought: humans, like other animals responded to conditioning (does the name Pavlov ring a bell?).

Seligman studied what he called learned helplessness, which he saw as a key factor in unipolar depression. People learnt to be helpless through failure, which led some to see all their actions as futile. Seligman believed that what could be learnt, could be unlearnt, and this was one of the key insights of what is now known as Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT). This is crucial to Duckworth's educational research: people learn bad, or negative behaviour, which affects their success in life, but this can be unlearnt.

Duckworth's work as a graduate student in 2004 was focussed on grit, which she defines as a combination of passion and perseverance. In that year [5] she gave a basic Grit Test to the incoming West Point cadets. Their first real test was the Barrack's Beast, a seven-week -period of gruelling physical and mental exertions. Despite the huge effort needed to get into West Point, nearly 20% will drop out before graduation, many after the Beast. Duckworth found that her Grit Test was a better predictor of success in the Beast than any other tests. Of course, an obvious objection to this is that the Beast is all about grit. The US Army makes the cadet's life miserable for seven weeks to see who was the staying power.

Duckworth went on to study other areas, with notable success, such as graduate sales trainees and Spelling Bee contestants. All showed that a high grit score was the best predictor of success. Duckworth is hardly the first to study success, as far back as 1869, Darwin's cousin Francis Galton studied the biographies of successful people, and concluded the key factors were: 'they demonstrate unusual "ability" in combination with exceptional "zeal" and "the capacity for hard labour.' Darwin wrote back to him: 'Darwin. "For I have always maintained that, excepting fools, men did not differ much in intellect, only in zeal and hard work; and I still think this is an eminently important difference.'

The American psychologist William James, brother of the novelist Henry, wrote at the end of the 19th century: 'The plain fact remains that men the world over possess amounts of resource, which only very exceptional individuals push to their extremes of use.'

Duckworth created her theory of grit after a bruising encounter with her supervisor, Seligman, who accused her of having none. She sat down to think about her research and came up with:

Figure 2: Talent and Effort, from [5]

"Talent is how quickly your skills improve when you invest effort. Achievement is what happens when you take your acquired skills and use them."

Duckworth, like Dweck, has devised a ten-item self-administered survey, with a five-point Likert response ranging from 'not at all like me' to 'very much like me.' Again, like Dweck, Duckworth has created a series of workshops for teaching grit, which has been shown to increase students overall academic performance.

Half the questions are on passion, and half on perseverance. Most gritty people score high on both, with most scoring slightly higher on perseverance. Interestingly, Duckworth doesn't focus on the intensity of passion, but on its long-term consistency. A good musician needs a passion for playing that enables years of practice, not an intense passion that is easily frustrated when the skills don't instantly appear.

Grit has four underlying components: Interest, practice, purpose and hope.

A person needs interest to begin, but purpose is required to maintain the application over time. And hope is required to overcome the inevitable setbacks that will occur.

Duckworth contends from her research that high Grit correlates with overall life satisfaction, which makes sense in that success encourages happiness more than failure does.

Figure 3: Life Satisfaction as a function of grit, from [5]

The American Psychological Association (APA) define five main personality characteristics, the so-called 'Big 5':

openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism (OCEAN).

Research has shown that Grit correlates strongly with self-control and conscientiousness, but Duckworth chose Grit as snappy and easy to relate to, especially for Americans.

In a 2014 report [6] for the Harvard Center for Educational Policy Research, Duckworth and others from Harvard and MIT looked at 1386 8th-grade students and surveye them for Grit and Mindset, as well as the traditional 'Big 5' personality traits of the APA. They also tested them for self-control, using the Impulsivity Scale for Children, an 8-item survey designed to measure school-age children's impulsivity, defined as the inability to "regulate behavior, attention, and emotions in the service of valued goals" [7]

The study found a good correlation between Mindset and Grit scores, with Pearson coefficients ranging from 0.43 to 0.66.

3.0 THE HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR IN IRELAND

Ireland has seven traditional universities, ranging from the oldest, Trinity College (TCD, founded in 1592) to the newest, NUI Maynooth (1997). Then there is the Dublin Institute of Technology, a member of the European Universities Association, with degree awarding powers to doctorate level as well as 13 other Institutes of Technology. There are also small private colleges and other independent colleges.

Admission to higher education in Ireland is via a central office; with access to programmes allocated on the basis of points obtained in the State Leaving Certificate examination (maximum attainable points were 600 over a range of six subjects, now 625 with a bonus for passing the higher level mathematics exams). Qualifications are graded according to a scheme devised by the National Qualifications Authority of Ireland (NQAI). In this scheme, Level 7 is an Ordinary bachelor degree, Level 8 is an Honours bachelor degree, Level 9 is a master's degree and Level 10 is a doctorate.

In this group, DIT has perhaps the most interesting history, having grown organically from a late 19th century group of technical colleges that dealt mainly with craft education, into a degree level institute – initially with degrees awarded by TCD. Since 1993, DIT has been a fully independent institution with degree-awarding powers, covering the full-range of higher education courses, from Level 6 certificates all the way to Level 10 doctorates.

3.1 THE DIT LEVEL 7 ENGINEERING STUDENT BODY

The first-year students of Mechanical Engineering in DIT constitute an above average (for level-7 nationally) group of students, with Leaving Certificate entry points typically around 350 (out of a maximum possible of 625). In the Academic year 2016-17, the number of students was 60, with an average of 354 points. It is also worth mentioning the overwhelming male bias of the 2016-17 class, with only five female students on the course in that year.

4.0 RESULTS

Students in the Level 7 Mechanical Engineering Programme in DIT in the academic year 2016-17 were given the standard Mindset and Grit survey forms. Their Mindset and Grit scores were then compared with their exam performance at the end of semester 1, in December 2016.

Both first year and third years had similar average Mindset scores, 31.41 and 29.65 respectively. This puts both classes into Dweck's category G1, of which she says: 'unsure you can change your intelligence; you care about your performance but you don't really want to work too hard to achieve it.' That sounds about right for our students.

The average Grit scores were different, with first years having an average of 41.79 and third years an average of 29.65. The Grit scale is from 1 to 5, with 5 being true grit and 1 a complete wimp. The first year score of 4.2 is quite gritty, although the third year score of 2.96 displays a certain lack of same.

The analysis for Grit and Semester1 Mathematics was:

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.054958766
R Square	0.003020466
Adjusted R Square	-
Standard Error	5.968942387
Observations	34

The analysis for Mindset and Semester1 Mathematics was:

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.149708171
R Square	0.022412536
Adjusted R Square	-
Standard Error	4.578670047
Observations	34

As can be seen, the effects for both Grit and Mindset are small, but Mindset is significantly larger, with Pearson coefficients of 0.149 v 0.0549.

It is worth mentioning here the work of Jacob Cohen in his 1988 book, *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. In Physics, an experiment to verify Ohm's law would result in Pearson coefficients well above 0.95; less than this would suggest faulty instruments or very poor technique. But in the social sciences, there is so much noise from a multiplicity of factors, that such 'perfect' correlations are almost never seen. Cohen [8] suggests the following for the social sciences:

Effect size	r
Small	0.10
Medium	0.30
Large	0.50

On Cohen's scale then, there is a small effect between Mindset and Mathematics in year one.

The results for the year 3 (final) students in Grit and Electrotechnology exam was:

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.248357497
R Square	0.061681446
Adjusted R Square	0.02258484
Standard Error	6.326840452
Observations	26

The results for the year 3 (final) students in Mindset and Electrotechnology exam was:

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.077362144
R Square	0.005984901
Adjusted R Square	-0.035432395
Standard Error	5.290870725
Observations	26

These results are more interesting, with Mindset showing weak correlation, but Grit, at 0.248, a medium effect. This suggests that the differences in first year are small, but over the course, Grit correlates better with academic achievement.

In fact, looking at the ANOVA for Mindset:

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	4.045102693	4.045102693	0.144502463	0.707188776
Residual	24	671.8395127		27.99331303	
Total	25		675.8846154		

It would be fair to accept the null hypothesis, H_0 , that Mindset has no effect on the exam outcome.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This is very much a preliminary work, and as they (probably) say in Lyon, *une hirondelle ne fait pas le printemps!*

However, it is interesting, even with a small amount of data, that the influence of Grit increases from first to final year, as one would expect from Dr. Duckworth's work. A larger student sample, over a period of two years will allow for a more robust analysis, and also the possibility for a longitudinal analysis.

It is over one hundred years since Alfred Binet produced the first standardised IQ test. Binet was motivated to create the test to identify weak students, so that they could be given extra teaching, to bring them up to the standard.

Binet's insight that intelligence is malleable has been shown in recent years by the American psychologist, James R. Flynn. In his 2009 book [9], *What is intelligence*, he discusses what is now known as the Flynn Effect, the massive rise in average IQ scores over the 20th Century. As Asbury and Plomin discovered as geneticists, genes determine that which is constant, environment that which is variable. Education will have succeeded when the only variation between students is genetic, not environmental. The challenge for educators is to so personalize students' education that that goal can be achieved.

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